

**TWENTY-SECOND YOUNG RESEARCHERS'
CONFERENCE
MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING**

December 4 – 6, 2024, Belgrade, Serbia

Program and the Book of Abstracts

**Materials Research Society of Serbia
&
Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA**

2024

Book title:

Twenty-Second Young Researchers' Conference - Materials Science and Engineering:
Program and the Book of Abstracts

Publisher:

Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA
Kneza Mihaila 35/IV, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia
Tel: +381-11-2636994, 2185263, <http://www.itn.sanu.ac.rs>

Conference organizers:

Materials Research Society of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia
Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Editor:

Dr. Smilja Marković

Technical Editor:

Aleksandra Stojičić and Dr. Ivana Dinić

Cover page: Dr. Smilja Marković

Cover photo: Dr. Nebojša Labus

Printing:

Gama digital centar
Otona Župančića No. 19, 11070 Belgrade, Serbia
Tel: +381-63 8616734
<http://www.gdc.rs>

Publication year: 2024

Print-run:

120 copies

CIP - Каталогизacija у публикацији

Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

66.017/.018(048)

YOUNG Researchers Conference Materials Sciences and Engineering (22 ; 2024 ; Beograd)

Program ; and the Book of abstracts / Twenty-Second Young Researchers' Conference Materials Science and Engineering, December 4 – 6, 2024, Belgrade, Serbia ; [organizers] Materials Research Society of Serbia & Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA ; [editor Smilja Marković]. - Belgrade : Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, 2024 (Belgrade : Gama digital centar). - XXII, 89 str. ; 23 cm Tiraž 120. - Registar.

ISBN 978-86-80321-39-4

а) Наука о материјалима -- Апстракти б) Технички материјали -- Апстракти
COBISS.SR-ID 157262345

Aim of the Conference

Main aim of the conference is to enable young researchers (post-graduate, master or doctoral student, or a PhD holder younger than 35) working in the field of materials science and engineering, to meet their colleagues and exchange experiences about their research.

Topics

Biomaterials
Environmental science
Materials for high-technology applications
Materials for new generation solar cells
Nanostructured materials
New synthesis and processing methods
Theoretical modelling of materials

Scientific and Organizing Committee

Committee President

Smilja Marković Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Vice-presidents

Ivana Dinić Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Sonja Jovanović Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, Belgrade, Serbia

Dorđe Veljović Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade, Serbia

Members

Katarina Cvetanović Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade, Serbia

Tatiana Demina Enikolopov Institute of Synthetic Polymeric Materials, Russian Academy of Sciences

Xuesen Du Chongqing University, Chongqing, China

Nenad Filipović Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Dragana Jugović Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Marijana Kraljić Roković Faculty of Chemical Engineering and Technology, Zagreb, Croatia

Snežana Lazić Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain

Lidija Mančić Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Bojan Marinković Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Marija Milanović Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia

Miloš Milović Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, Belgrade, Serbia

Jelena Mitrić Institute of Physics, Belgrade, Serbia

Nebojša Mitrović Faculty of Technical Sciences, Čačak, Serbia

Irena Nikolić Faculty of Metallurgy and Technology, Podgorica, Montenegro

Marko Opačić Institute of Physics, Belgrade, Serbia

Alexander Osmolovskiy Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Russia

Vuk Radmilović Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade, Serbia

Milan Radovanović	Technical Faculty in Bor, Serbia
Vladimir Rajić	Institute of Nuclear Sciences “Vinča”, Belgrade, Serbia
Julietta Rau	Institute of the Structure of Matter of the Italian National Research Council (ISM-CNR), Rome, Italy
Ana Stanković	Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia
Boban Stojanović	Faculty of Sciences, Kragujevac, Serbia
Ivana Stojković Simatović	Faculty of Physical Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia
Srečo Škapin	Institute Jožef Stefan, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Konrad Terpiłowski	Department of Interfacial Phenomena, Institute of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Chemistry, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University in Lublin, Poland
Vuk Uskoković	TardigradeNano, Irvine, CA, USA
Rastko Vasilic	Faculty of Physics, Belgrade, Serbia
Ljiljana Veselinović	Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia
<u>Conference Secretary</u>	
Aleksandra Stojičić	Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Belgrade, Serbia

Conference Technical Committee

Katarina Aleksić, Marija Grujičić, Marko Jelić, Tamara Matić, Željko Mravik, Ana Nastasić, Milica Pejčić, Miljana Piljević, Jelena Rmuš-Mravik, Nina Tomić.

Results of the Conference

Beside printed «Program and the Book of Abstracts», which is disseminated to all conference participants, selected and awarded peer-reviewed papers will be published in journal “Tehnika – Novi Materijali”. The best presented papers, suggested by Session Chairpersons and selected by Awards Committee, will be proclaimed at the Closing Ceremony. Part of the award is free-of-charge conference fee at YUCOMAT 2025.

Sponsors

ANALYSIS
LABORATORY EQUIPMENT

TEVUS
lab science

Acknowledgement

The editor and the publisher of the Book of abstracts are grateful to the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia for its financial support of this book and The Twenty-Second Young Researchers' Conference - Materials Sciences and Engineering, held in Belgrade, Serbia.

9-2

Quinuclidinone thiosemicarbazone hydrate: Insights into crystal structure from an energetic perspective

Milica G. Bogdanović¹, Vidak N. Raičević², Guido J. Reiss³, Marko V. Rodić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

³Institute for Inorganic Chemistry, Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany

The hydrate form of quinuclidinone thiosemicarbazone was synthesized following established procedures and successfully isolated in pure form. The compound crystallizes in the orthorhombic $P2_12_12_1$ space group, with the asymmetric unit containing one organic molecule (A) and one water molecule (W). During the refinement process, both the conventional independent atom model (IAM) and quantum crystallographic method Hirshfeld atom refinement (HAR) were used. HAR provided notable improvements in both geometry and refinement statistics, particularly for hydrogen atoms, which were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters and without constraints. Interaction energies between the nearest neighbors of A and W molecules in the crystal structure were calculated using the hybrid method in *CrystalExplorer* as well as DFT with a def2-TZVP basis set and M06-2X functional. Seven interactions with energies stronger than -10 kJ mol^{-1} were identified. The strongest interaction is found between molecules A and A, mediated through two hydrogen bonds (N–H \cdots N and N–H \cdots S) with a total energy of -39 kJ mol^{-1} . The second strongest interaction in the crystal structure, with $E = -30 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, occurs between A and W molecules, via N–H \cdots O. Weaker interactions (-25 kJ mol^{-1} and -22 kJ mol^{-1}) are also mediated by hydrogen bonds (O–H \cdots N and O–H \cdots S) between W and A. All these interactions are primarily influenced by electrostatic energy contributions, indicating that hydrogen bonds play a critical role in both the geometric arrangement and energetic stabilization of the crystal packing. Additionally, three weaker interactions occur between A molecules, with approximately equal contributions from electrostatic and dispersion components to the total energy.

Acknowledgement: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-66/2024-03/200125 & 451-03-65/2024-03/200125), and German–Serbian joint scientific co-operation project: Application of quantum- crystallographic methods in extended routine X-ray structural analysis of small molecules (Grant No. 337-00-253/2023-05/12).